

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION COMMUNICATIVE TECHNOLOGY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING

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Abstract. *This article about the Information and Communication Technology, or ICT, refers to technological tools that are used to communicate and to manage information. ICT is often part of a teacher-centred class but it is easy to exploit these tools in learner-centred activities.*

Keywords: *ICT, digital work, students' ability, project, usage of ICT, tools, techniques, approaches, method, class project.*

Language is the mirror of human life which delineates the life of human. Language speaks man's personality. It is the cosmic medium like imparting the common information society. English and ICT have become essential tools for a number of non-datum and emotions of everyday life. English language has become a global language because of its numerous functions and preferences over several other languages over the globe. English has become the window to the world. English is not only the mother tongue of Britain but also to so many countries like Canada, USA, New Zealand etc. It is also used as second language in many countries like Nigeria, Ghana etc. English has become a medium for business and interactional purposes among other functions. English is playing a major role in every field such as medicine, engineering, education, art and law, music etc. As the world is changing, there must be changes in language learning. But contemporaneous collide of globalization, the expanse of English and technological development have transformed our learning and teaching English as a Lingua franca in an unprecedented way. In every aspect of human life, Science, Information, Technology are playing a vital role. Even in the field of education the technological developments have started a new page. Traditional methods of teaching are not showing great impact on the learners. Technology has become a tool for making the learners innovative and also became a source for motivating the learners towards learning. To compete with these native speakers of English.

“With the help of technology, teachers will be leaders in the transformation of education around the world”-Craig Barrett ICT means Information and Communication Technology. According to Kent, “ICT in education point of view refers to Information and Communication Technology such as computers, communications facilities and features that variously support teaching learning and a range of activities in education [QCA schemes of work for ICT in Kent country council,2004]. Because of its interactive and dynamic nature ICT has the stamina to meet the needs of the individual student by providing opportunities to direct their learning and to pursue information. With the usage of ICT students can learn any subject especially English with ease. In the context of the global exchange the role of ICT has become inevitable in the 21st century. The use of ICT has become essential in every day classroom teaching and learning. Its use gives a chance to teachers as well as students to increase the quality of education and meet the requirements set by the coeval knowledge society. ICT has become essential tool for educational change and reform.

According to Jeremy Harmer, “a word innovation means something new, which means new ideas to change things for better. “He claims that “if we look at all the language teaching methods which are used all over the world by different teachers at different levels, we cannot say that all of them are 100% successful. Therefore, it is very important to keep looking and searching to find ways to make teaching and learning better.” Government has included ICT as one of the curricula in Indonesia’s education. The Methodology of English has started a new way of using ICT in teaching. ICT provides more opportunities for communication between peer learners. With the use of ICT there is a two-way exchange of knowledge between home and school/ college. The teacher abides key to the successful use of ICT for learning. The integration of ICT in language teaching and learning has become an interesting topic to many researchers and education practitioners.

Computer Assisted Language Learning: CALL is a broad and an ever changing discipline. Beatty defines, CALL as “Any process in which a learner uses a computer and as a result improves his or her language and it covers the wide range of current practice in the field. “The internet and different computer applications. Computer Assisted language learning(CALL) software, CD-ROMS ,and Office software applications have become common place in many teaching and learning environments. The computer can act as a stimulus which generates analysis, discussion and writing. The Internet : The internet offers the best way to learn language other than immersion in an English speaking milieu. The student’s relationship with websites is more noticeable than with print-based text. Internet users may return to sites frequently or use internet for interaction to share their information and ideas. Digital technology is rapidly used by pupils and teachers not only in the classroom but also in the personal life. The advantages of online learning: The internet saves our time and energy. we can learn English lessons through internet without the need of travelling and without the need of leaving home or bedroom. With internet students can learn English anywhere at any time and whenever they want. The internet offers instant feedback to the learners which enhance the learning experience of the students. EBooks An eBook is an electronic version of a traditional print book that can be read by using a personal or by using an eBook reader like iPods and kindle. EBooks also used to improve the teaching and learning skills in the classroom. In eBooks teachers and students can add images, info graphics, IJSER International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, Volume 7, Issue 7, July-2016 3 ISSN 2229-5518 IJSER © 2016 <http://www.ijser.org> posters, video, and text, audio and so on. Learners can share eBooks with their friends. EBooks strengthen students’ note making skills, the knowledge of English grammar and application skills. Audio Books: Baskin and Harris (1995:372) explain, “The first literature heard, not read. ”Audio books are not discovery of this century or even of the last one considering authentic books as equivalent to its content and not to its format (Baskin and Harris1995:372).Audio books are applicable for English language learners and young people who are craving for learning English with stories. Audio books develop the four language systems; phonological, semantic, syntactic and pragmatic. Audio books are recordings on CD or digital file of a book which are read aloud. “The use of audio books with struggling, reluctant or second language learners is powerful since they act as a scaffold that allows students to read above their actual reading level” (Beers 998:33, Chen Slu-Hsien 2004). Play way is the new arrival regarding audio books. Play way does not need a separate player and it is preloaded and ready to use. Webinar: Webinar is the best example for online learning. Webinar is an interactive seminar conducted via the World Wide Web. Usually a live presentation, lecture or work-shop that,

happens in real time as users participate through chatting, video-chatting, file-sharing or asking questions with a microphone. Webinars are more helpful in learning grammar. Interactive White Board: Gareth Davis says that “IWB brings everything together at one placemat one time with the use of authentic materials. “IWB acts as a motivational tool. IWB has to be connected to the computer and data projector. IWB offers teachers to comprise video clips, films interviews, electronic microscopes, different websites etc. It improves the social skills of the students like cooperation and participation. In IWB lessons can be recorded and saved for further use. Bactra states that the power of images and capacity for collaboration is very significant in White Board’s impact on learning. “IWB teaching is completely different from traditional methods of teaching. According to Cunnings worth “vocabulary was a neglected area of foreign language teaching but it has gained its due recognition in the last few years” (1998:38). New vocabulary, word formation and sounds are practiced easily by IWB. Mobile Apps Mobile digital devices like laptops, iPods, tablets, smart phones have made English language learning easier. At present there are so many apps available in the App store and Play store (Android) markets. These apps furnish students with quizzes, games, dictionaries, Podcasts and tests. Some mobile apps which are amending English language learning and teaching are Dictionary.com, Hangman, Grammar’s, Quizmaster, 60-Second Word Challenge, Mobile Air Mouse, Ankhil Flash Cards, English Idioms Illustrated etc. Audio-visual aids: In the 21st century the use of AVA has become inevitable. It has started a new genre in the field of teaching and learning language. Apart from traditional teaching teachers must adopt the topical and innovative teaching techniques. 1 The use of AVA makes the students active. 2 Students can get rid of their boredom and dullness in the class. 3 Provide attentiveness and enthusiasm. 4. They help to nurture the power of surveillance and independent judgment. 5. They give clarification about the content in the text book.

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